
REDEFINING SOCIO-POLITICAL WILL FOR EFFECTIVE COMPLIANCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL LAWS IN PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Research is necessary because environmental law is so intricate on several levels of complexity including legal, scientific, socio-political, geographical and economical. Environmental jurists, judges, lawyers, legislatures, executives, environmentalists and experts need a rational, intellectual approach and research to understand and highlight these complexities with sustainable solutions. Environmentalists come forward to explain the complex ecological and socio-political nature of environmental problems and the interrelationships between such problems and different aspects of relevant legal systems, including different attempts to regulate these problems through law. The discourse requires redefining the multiple contexts in which environmental laws operates and the perspectives that can be validly brought to bear in the understanding of the subject, as well as the engagement of all participants in effective compliance with the environmental laws of Pakistan. The experts come to provide insight to provoke thinking about environmental laws by exposing the themes, issues, and novel legal problems of the subject, providing good quality research material that illustrates the complexity of environmental problems and the laws that applies to them, and also provide an analytical framework for the understanding of that complexity and compliance of environmental laws of Pakistan.

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